

ON THREE FORMULAS FOR MELLIN INTEGRAL TRANSFORM AND ITS INVERSION

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ABSTRACT. Using a group-theoretic approach, we provide new proofs for three known formulas. The first formula, which can be traced back to the Mellin or Meijer integral transform, emerges from the relationship between the Q -images of two functions belonging to distinct bases in the first representation space, where Q is the special linear operator, which maps the first representation space into the second. Both functions are parameterized by two variables, and the formula is derived by setting these parameters to zero for the first function. The second and third formulas follow a similar pattern, relating to the inversion of the Mellin transform for the product of two or four gamma functions (Barnes integrals). Additionally, we explore generalizations of these formulas for other parameter values.

1. INTRODUCTION

It is not an overstatement to observe that many special functions in number theory and mathematical physics are intricately linked to representation group theory. For instance, by considering the equality $g(0, b)g(0, 1) = g(0, b + 1)$ for the multiplicative group of matrices

$$g(a, b) = \begin{pmatrix} e^a & b \\ 0 & 1 \end{pmatrix}, \quad a, b \in \mathbb{R},$$

Vilenkin [9, Chapter 5], using the representation of this group (see also [3, Example 3.1]), demonstrated the group-theoretic interpretation of the following formula for the inverse Mellin integral transform:

$$\int_{a+i\infty}^{a-i\infty} \Gamma(t)\Gamma(s-t) dt = 2^{1-s} \pi i \Gamma(s) \quad (0 < a < \Re(s)),$$

which can be viewed as a continual addition theorem for the gamma function.

Recently [7, 8] we provided new proofs for the following known formulas (see [5, Entries 2.16.21.2, 2.16.2.2, and 2.16.33.2]) for Meijer integral transforms:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} K_{-\sigma-1/2}(t) J_{-\sigma-1/2}(t) dt = \frac{\sqrt{\pi} \Gamma(-\frac{\sigma}{2})}{4 \Gamma(\frac{1-\sigma}{2})};$$

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$$\int_0^{+\infty} t^{-1/2} K_{\sigma+1/2}(t) dt = 2^{-3/2} \Gamma\left(-\frac{\sigma}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(\frac{1+\sigma}{2}\right) \quad (-1 < \Re(\sigma) < 0);$$

$$\int_0^{+\infty} [K_{\frac{\sigma+1}{2}}(t)]^2 dt = 2^{-2} \pi \Gamma\left(-\frac{\sigma}{2}\right) \Gamma\left(1 + \frac{\sigma}{2}\right).$$

where $J_\xi(t)$ is the Bessel function of the first kind, and $K_\xi(t)$ is the modified Bessel function of the second kind. We also obtained some generalizations of these formulas.

In the current paper, by using the same approach, we provide a new derivation of three known formulas (see [1, Entry 6.8.45], [6, Entry 2.2.1.1], and [1, Entry 7.3.17]) for the Mellin transform and its inversion. The first of them can also be considered a Meijer integral transform, and other two formulas are Barnes integrals. We show that these formulas can be interpreted as a special case of the relationship between the Q -images of the basis functions of a space, where Q is a linear operator intertwining two representations of the same group. This special case is obtained for zero parameter values. For arbitrary admissible parameter values, generalizations of these formulas are obtained, one of which is given below.

Well-known monographs [1] and [2] describe in detail how the formulas discussed in current article or similar ones are derived: contour integration in the complex plane, series expansion, term-by-term differentiation and integration, etc. are used. We emphasize that in current article we reveal the group-theoretical foundations of these formulas.

2. THE REPRESENTATION SPACES L_1 AND L_2

Fixing a non-degenerate matrix a , we consider the set of matrices b , referred to as a -matrices, that satisfy the condition $b^\top ab = a$ [7]. It is straightforward to verify that $|\det b| = 1$. Furthermore, this set forms a subgroup G_a within $GL(n, \mathbb{R})$. For example, $G_a = O(n)$ when a is the identity matrix I_n . Similarly, $G_a = Sp(n, \mathbb{R})$ when a is composed of diagonal blocks that are zero matrices and off-diagonal blocks that are $I_{n/2}$ and $-I_{n/2}$, respectively.

In this paper, we focus on the case where a is a diagonal matrix with blocks I_1 and $-I_3$. In this case, for any $(g_{ij}) \in G_a$, the following relation holds:

$$g_{i1}g_{j1} - g_{i2}g_{j2} - g_{i3}g_{j3} - g_{i4}g_{j4} = (-1)^{1-\delta_{i1}\delta_{ij}}.$$

From this equality, we deduce that the matrices g from G_a , which satisfy the conditions $\det(g) = 1$ and $g_{11} > 0$, form a subgroup G acting transitively on the cone $\mathcal{X}^\circ : x_1 = \sqrt{x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2}$, where $x_1 \neq 0$, as well as on the hyperboloid $\mathcal{Y} : y_1 = \sqrt{1 + y_2^2 + y_3^2 + y_4^2}$.

Let f be a function defined on \mathcal{X}° . We refer to f as an infinitely differentiable function if, for every set of non-negative integers k_1, k_2, k_3 , where $(k_1, k_2, k_3) \neq (0, 0, 0)$, f has a continuous derivative:

$$\frac{\partial^{k_1+k_2+k_3} f}{\partial x_1^{k_1} \partial x_2^{k_2} \partial x_3^{k_3}}$$

at any point within its domain. Let $\sigma \in \mathbb{C}$ be fixed. We call f σ -homogeneous if $f(\lambda x) = \lambda^\sigma f(x)$, where $\lambda > 0$ since $x_1 > 0$. We denote L_1 as the linear space of σ -homogeneous infinitely differentiable functions on \mathcal{X}° , and L_2 as the space of infinitely differentiable functions on \mathcal{Y} .

Finally, we define the representations $T_i : G \rightarrow \text{Aut } L_i$ by the formula:

$$T_i(g) : L_i \rightarrow L_i, \quad f(x) \mapsto f(gx).$$

Let $H^{(1)}$ be the stabilizer of the vertex $\tilde{y} = (1, 0, 0, 0) \in \mathcal{Y}$. Then, for each $h \in G$, the left coset $hH^{(1)}$ consists of all matrices that map \tilde{y} to a fixed point

$$(\cosh \theta_1, \sinh \theta_1 \sinh \theta_2 \sin \theta_3, \sinh \theta_1 \sin \theta_2 \cos \theta_3, \sinh \theta_1 \cos \theta_2)$$

in \mathcal{Y} . The subgroup $H^{(1)}$ is isomorphic to $SO(3)$, and therefore, it is a 3-parameter subgroup. An element h that generates the coset $hH^{(1)}$ can be represented in the form:

$$h = h_{23}(\theta_3)h_{34}(\theta_2)h_{14}(\theta_1),$$

where h_{14} is a hyperbolic rotation in the plane Ox_1x_4 by an angle θ_1 , and h_{23}, h_{34} are circular rotations in the planes Ox_2x_3 and Ox_3x_4 by angles θ_2 and θ_3 , respectively. Thus, G is a 6-parameter group. Next, we define e_{ij} , where $i, j \in \{2, 3, 4\}$, as the tangent vectors at the identity matrix for one-parameter subgroups $H_{i,j}$ in G , consisting of circular rotations in the planes Ox_ix_j , respectively. Let e_{1i} , where $i \in \{2, 3, 4\}$, be the tangent vector at the identity matrix for the subgroup H_i consisting of hyperbolic rotations in the plane Ox_1x_i . These 6 tangent vectors form a basis for the tangent Lie algebra \mathfrak{g} . The infinitesimal operators of the representation T_1 corresponding to these vectors are given by:

$$\begin{aligned} \mathfrak{d}_{ij} f &= \mathbf{i} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{T_1(\exp(te_{ij})) f(x) - f(x)}{t}, \\ \mathfrak{d}_i f &= \mathbf{i} \lim_{t \rightarrow 0} \frac{T_1(\exp(te_i)) f(x) - f(x)}{t}. \end{aligned}$$

The linear subspace $\mathfrak{k} = \text{Span}(e_{2,3}, e_{2,4}, e_{3,4})$ in \mathfrak{g} forms a subalgebra. To simplify the notation, let us introduce the following alternative notations: $\tilde{e}_i = e_{jk}$ for $i \neq j$ and $i \neq k$, and $\tilde{e}_i = e_{i+2}$. In particular,

$$[\tilde{e}_1, \tilde{e}_2] = \tilde{e}_3, \quad [\tilde{e}_1, \tilde{e}_3] = -\tilde{e}_2, \quad [\tilde{e}_2, \tilde{e}_3] = \tilde{e}_1, \quad (2.1)$$

$$[\tilde{e}_2, \tilde{e}_4] = 0, \quad [\tilde{e}_3, \tilde{e}_5] = 0, \quad [\tilde{e}_4, \tilde{e}_5] = \tilde{e}_1. \quad (2.2)$$

Similar notations will be used for the corresponding infinitesimal operators.

Calculating the structure constants of the algebra \mathfrak{g} from the relations $[\tilde{e}_i, \tilde{e}_j] = \sum_{k=1}^6 c_{ij}^k \tilde{e}_k$, we obtain the Killing metric matrix $(d_{ij}) = \text{diag}(-2, -2, -2)$, where

$$d_{ij} = \sum_{k,l=1}^3 c_{ik}^l c_{jl}^k.$$

We consider the intersection γ_1 of the cone \mathcal{X}° and the sphere $x_1^2 + x_2^2 + x_3^2 + x_4^2 = 2$ as a homogeneous space of the subgroup $H^{(1)} = \exp \mathfrak{k}$. Given that $\mathfrak{d}_{ij} = -\mathbf{i} \left(x_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_j} - x_j \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} \right)$

and $\mathfrak{d}_i = \mathbf{i} \left(x_1 \frac{\partial}{\partial x_i} + x_i \frac{\partial}{\partial x_1} \right)$, the Casimir operator of the subalgebra $\text{Span}(\tilde{e}_1)$ in spherical coordinates $x_1 = 1, x_2 = \sin \alpha \sin \beta, x_3 = \sin \alpha \cos \beta, x_4 = \cos \alpha$ (with $\alpha, \beta \in (-\pi, \pi]$) on γ_1 takes the form $\mathfrak{c}_1 = \tilde{\mathfrak{d}}_1 = \mathbf{i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta}$. Since, in view of (2.1), the vectors \tilde{e}_1, \tilde{e}_2 and \tilde{e}_3 forming the basis of the algebra \mathfrak{k} do not commute with each other, there is no second first-order Casimir differential operator corresponding to the reduction $G \supset H^{(1)} \supset H_{2,3}$. The simplest Casimir operator of the full subalgebra \mathfrak{k} is the quadratic differential operator:

$$\mathfrak{c}_2 = \sum_{i,j=1}^3 d_{ij}^{\text{inv}} \tilde{\mathfrak{d}}_i \tilde{\mathfrak{d}}_j,$$

where $(d_{ij}^{\text{inv}}) = (d_{ij})^{-1}$. Up to a numerical factor, we obtain:

$$\mathfrak{c}_2 = \mathfrak{d}_{2,3}^2 + \mathfrak{d}_{2,4}^2 + \mathfrak{d}_{3,4}^2 = - \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + \text{ctg } \alpha \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} + \text{cosec}^2 \alpha \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} \right).$$

Let f_{\downarrow} be a restriction of the function $f \in L_1$ to γ_1 . We assume that f_{\downarrow} is a common eigenfunction of the operators \mathfrak{c}_1 and \mathfrak{c}_2 . By applying the method of separation of variables, we find f_{\downarrow} in the form $f_{\downarrow} = A(\alpha)B(\beta)$. It follows that $B(\beta) \in \text{Span}(e^{i\lambda\beta})$, where $\lambda \in \mathbb{Z}$. Let us consider the family of $k+1$ common eigenfunctions of operators \mathfrak{c}_1 and \mathfrak{c}_2 , whose eigenvalues with respect to \mathfrak{c}_1 are $\lambda, \lambda+1, \dots, \lambda+k$, respectively. We denote these eigenfunctions as $f_{\downarrow\lambda}, \dots, f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}$. Introducing the differential operators $\mathfrak{d}_{\pm} = \mathfrak{d}_{2,4} \pm \mathbf{i}\mathfrak{d}_{3,4}$, we have

$$\mathfrak{d}_{\pm} f_{\downarrow\lambda} \in \text{Span}(f_{\downarrow\lambda \pm 1}). \quad (2.3)$$

Supposing that the linear subspace $\text{Span}(f_{\downarrow\lambda}, \dots, f_{\downarrow\lambda+k})$ is invariant under the actions of \mathfrak{d}_+ and \mathfrak{d}_- , we obtain the following conditions:

$$\mathfrak{d}_- f_{\downarrow\lambda} = 0, \quad \mathfrak{d}_+ f_{\downarrow\lambda+k} = 0. \quad (2.4)$$

From (2.3), it follows that $\mathfrak{c}_2 \mathfrak{d}_+ f_{\downarrow\lambda} = \mathfrak{c}_2 \nu f_{\downarrow\lambda+1}$, and also that $\mathfrak{d}_+ \mathfrak{c}_2 f_{\downarrow\lambda} = (\lambda^2 - \lambda) \nu f_{\downarrow\lambda+1}$. Since $[\mathfrak{c}_2, \mathfrak{d}_+] = 0$, the eigenfunction $f_{\downarrow\lambda+1}$ of the operator \mathfrak{c}_2 corresponds to the eigenvalue $\lambda^2 - \lambda \geq 0$ (as does $f_{\downarrow\lambda}$). By induction, we conclude that the full family of eigenfunctions $f_{\downarrow\lambda}, \dots, f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}$ of the operator \mathfrak{c}_2 corresponds to the eigenvalue $\lambda^2 - \lambda$. According to (2.4), we have:

$$\mathfrak{c}_2 f_{\downarrow\lambda+k} = ((\lambda+k)^2 + (\lambda+k)) f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}.$$

Using (2.3), we derive:

$$\mathfrak{c}_2 \mathfrak{d}_- f_{\downarrow\lambda+k} = ((\lambda+k)^2 + (\lambda+k)) \mu f_{\downarrow\lambda+k-1}.$$

Since $[\mathfrak{c}_2, \mathfrak{d}_-] = 0$, it follows that the eigenfunction $f_{\downarrow\lambda+k-1}$ of the operator \mathfrak{c}_2 corresponds to the eigenvalue $(\lambda+k)^2 + (\lambda+k)$, as does $f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}$. By induction, we conclude that the full family of eigenfunctions $f_{\downarrow\lambda}, \dots, f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}$ of the operator \mathfrak{c}_2 corresponds to the eigenvalue $(\lambda+k)^2 + (\lambda+k)$.

Solving the equation $\lambda^2 - \lambda = (\lambda+k)^2 + (\lambda+k)$, we find $k = -2\lambda$. We will refer to $|\lambda|$ as the radius of the family $f_{\downarrow\lambda}, \dots, f_{\downarrow\lambda+k}$. Based on the reasoning above, it follows that the complete set of common eigenfunctions of the operators \mathfrak{c}_1 and \mathfrak{c}_2 can be divided into a countable set of classes.

The *first class* contains a single eigenfunction, whose eigenvalues with respect to both operators are zero. The radius is 0.

The *second class* contains 3 eigenfunctions, which correspond to eigenvalues -1 , 0 , and 1 with respect to \mathfrak{c}_1 , and to the eigenvalue 2 with respect to \mathfrak{c}_2 . The radius is 1.

The *third class* contains 5 eigenfunctions, which correspond to eigenvalues 0 , ± 1 , and ± 2 with respect to \mathfrak{c}_1 , and to the eigenvalue 6 with respect to \mathfrak{c}_2 . The radius is 2.

And so on.

Let us introduce the following numbering of common eigenfunctions: let the first index p represent the radius of the class to which the eigenfunction belongs, and the second index q represent the eigenvalue which corresponds to this eigenfunction with respect to \mathfrak{c}_1 . These common eigenfunctions form a basis $\{f_{\downarrow(p,q)}^{(1)} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{Z}, p \geq 0, |q| \leq p\}$ in the space of restrictions of functions from L_1 to γ_1 .

To determine the A-part of each basis function $f_{\downarrow(p,q)}^{(1)}$, we find, for all p , a particular solution of the following differential equation:

$$\frac{\partial^2 f_{\downarrow(p,q)}}{\partial \alpha^2} + \operatorname{ctg} \alpha \frac{\partial f_{\downarrow(p,q)}}{\partial \alpha} + \operatorname{cosec}^2 \alpha \frac{\partial^2 f_{\downarrow(p,q)}}{\partial \beta^2} = -p(p+1) f_{\downarrow(p,q)}.$$

After substituting $t = \cos \alpha$, the corresponding equation

$$\frac{d^2 A}{d\alpha^2} + \operatorname{ctg} \alpha \frac{dA}{d\alpha} - \frac{q^2 A}{\sin^2 \alpha} = -p(p+1) A$$

for the A-part takes the form

$$\frac{d}{dt} \left((1-t^2) \frac{dA}{dt} \right) + \left(p(p+1) - \frac{q^2}{1-t^2} \right) A = 0.$$

By applying the substitution $A = (1-t^2)^{|q|/2} \hat{A}$ (see [2, Section 5.8.6]), we obtain the equation:

$$(1-t^2) \frac{d^2 \hat{A}}{dt^2} - 2(|q|+1)t \frac{d\hat{A}}{dt} + (p-|q|)(p+|q|+1) \hat{A} = 0,$$

where a particular solution is given by the Gegenbauer polynomial $C_{p-|q|}^{|q|+1/2}(t)$. Considering the σ -homogeneity property of functions from L_1 , it follows that

$$f_{(p,q)}^{(1)}(x) = x_1^\sigma f_{\downarrow(p,q)}^{(1)}.$$

Consequently, we obtain the basis $B_1 = \{f_{(p,q)}^{(1)} \mid p, q \in \mathbb{Z}, p \geq 0, |q| \leq p\}$, where the functions $f_{(p,q)}^{(1)}(x)$ are expressed as

$$\begin{aligned} f_{p,q}^{(1)}(x) &= x_1^\sigma \sin^{|q|/2} \alpha C_{p-|q|}^{|q|+1/2}(\cos \alpha) e^{iq\beta} \\ &= x_1^\sigma C_{p-|q|}^{|q|+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{x_4}{x_1} \right) \left(\frac{x_3}{x_1} + \mathbf{i} \operatorname{sign} q \frac{x_2}{x_1} \right)^{|q|} \\ &= x_1^{\sigma-|q|} (x_3 + \mathbf{i} x_2 \operatorname{sign} q)^{|q|} C_{p-|q|}^{|q|+\frac{1}{2}} \left(\frac{x_4}{x_1} \right). \end{aligned}$$

Note that the algebra \mathfrak{k} and its complementary linear subspace define a \mathbb{Z}_2 -grading of the algebra \mathfrak{g} . Since the complementary linear subspace is spanned by vectors e_2 ,

e_3 and e_4 , and $\text{Ker ad } e_i = \text{Span}(e_i)$, the real rank of G is equal to 1. Consequently, the dimension of a maximal commutative subalgebra \mathfrak{a} in \mathfrak{g} is 1. Any non-zero vector in the complementary linear subspace can be chosen as a generating element of \mathfrak{a} . Let $\mathfrak{a} = \text{Span}(\tilde{e}_6)$. Then the maximal nilpotent subalgebra \mathfrak{n} is the linear space consisting of the zero vector and eigenvectors of the adjoint operator $\text{ad } \tilde{e}_6$ corresponding to the eigenvalue -1 . Specifically, this implies that

$$\mathfrak{n} = \text{Span}(\tilde{e}_2 + \tilde{e}_5, \tilde{e}_3 + \tilde{e}_4).$$

Since, in view of (2.1)–(2.2), the vectors $\tilde{e}_2 + \tilde{e}_5$ and $\tilde{e}_3 + \tilde{e}_4$, generating the subalgebra \mathfrak{n} , commute with each other, the subgroup $H^{(2)} = \exp \mathfrak{n}$ consists of matrices:

$$h^{(2)}(\mu, \nu) = \frac{1}{2} \begin{pmatrix} 2 + \mu^2 + \nu^2 & 2\mu & 2\nu & \mu^2 + \nu^2 & \\ & 2\mu & 2 & 0 & 2\mu \\ & 2\nu & 0 & 2 & 2\nu \\ -\mu^2 - \nu^2 & -2\mu & -2\nu & 2 - \mu^2 - \nu^2 & \end{pmatrix}.$$

As a homogeneous space of the subgroup $H^{(2)}$ we can specify the intersection γ_2 of this cone with the plane $x_1 + x_4 = 1$. Introducing the orispherical coordinates:

$$x_1 = \frac{1 + \alpha^2}{2}, \quad x_2 = \alpha \sin \beta, \quad x_3 = \alpha \cos \beta, \quad x_4 = \frac{1 - \alpha^2}{2},$$

where $\alpha \in \mathbb{R}$ and $\beta \in (-\pi, \pi]$, we obtain, as done for the subgroup $H^{(1)}$, the Casimir operators

$$\mathfrak{c}_1 = \mathfrak{d}_{2,3} = \mathbf{i} \frac{\partial}{\partial \beta},$$

and

$$\mathfrak{c}_2 = (\mathfrak{d}_{2,4} + \mathfrak{d}_2)^2 + (\mathfrak{d}_{3,4} + \mathfrak{d}_3)^2 = - \left(\frac{\partial^2}{\partial \alpha^2} + \frac{1}{\alpha} \frac{\partial}{\partial \alpha} + \frac{1}{\alpha^2} \frac{\partial^2}{\partial \beta^2} \right),$$

corresponding to the reduction $G \supset H^{(2)} \supset H_{2,3}$.

Let f_{\downarrow} be the restriction of $f \in L_1$ on γ_2 such that f_{\downarrow} is a common eigenfunction of both operators \mathfrak{c}_1 and \mathfrak{c}_2 . From the equalities $\mathfrak{c}_1 f_{\downarrow} = \omega f_{\downarrow}$ and $\mathfrak{c}_2 f_{\downarrow} = \lambda f_{\downarrow}$, we derive the following equation for the A-part of the function $f_{\downarrow} = A(\alpha)B(\beta)$:

$$\alpha^2 \frac{d^2 A}{d\alpha^2} + \alpha \frac{dA}{d\alpha} + (\omega \alpha^2 - \lambda^2)A = 0. \quad (2.5)$$

As is known, an equation of the form (2.5) arises (as the equation for the radial part) when solving the wave equation $\Delta u(r, \varphi) = -\mu u(r, \varphi)$ by the method of separation of variables and has a non-zero solution only for $\mu > 0$. Therefore, $\omega \geq 0$. Let $p = \sqrt{\omega}$. Then one of the solutions of equation (2.5) [2, Section 7.1] is the function $J_{|\lambda|}(p\alpha)$. Supposing $q = \lambda$ and lifting f_{\downarrow} to full cone \mathcal{X}° , we obtain the basis $B_2 = \{f_{(p,q)}^{(2)} \mid p > 0, q \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ in L_1 , which consists of functions:

$$f_{p,q}^{(2)}(x) = |x_1 + x_4|^\sigma (x_2^2 + x_3^2)^{-|q|/2} (x_3 + \mathbf{i} x_2 \text{sign } q_2)^{|q|} J_{|q|} \left(\frac{p \sqrt{x_2^2 + x_3^2}}{x_1 + x_4} \right).$$

By analogy, we can construct the basis $B_3 = \{f_{(p,q)}^{(3)} \mid p \in \mathbb{R}, q \in \mathbb{Z}\}$ in L_1 , where the elements are given by

$$f_{(p,q)}^{(3)}(x) = (x_1^2 - x_4^2)^{\frac{\sigma-q-ip}{2}} (x_1 + x_4)^{ip} (x_3 + ix_2)^q.$$

These functions extend from γ_3 to \mathcal{X}° as common eigenfunctions of the Casimir operators corresponding to the reduction $G \supset H^{(3)} \supset H_{2,3}$. Here, $H^{(3)} = H_4 \times H_{2,3}$, and its homogeneous space γ_3 on the cone \mathcal{X}° is defined as

$$\gamma_3 = \{(\cosh \alpha, \sin \beta, \cos \beta, \sinh \alpha) \mid \alpha \in \mathbb{R}, \beta \in (-\pi, \pi]\}.$$

3. A MELLIN TRANSFORM OF THE SQUARED MACDONALD FUNCTION

By replacing σ with the $-\sigma - 2$ in the definition of the space L_1 , we define a new space L_1^* , which is analogous to it. In this section, we utilize the bilinear functionals $F_i : L_1 \times L_1^* \rightarrow \mathbb{C}$, defined as

$$(u, v^*) \mapsto \int_{\gamma_i} u(x) v^*(x) dx,$$

where dx denotes an $H^{(i)}$ -invariant measure on γ_i . Additionally, for the fixed point $y \in \mathcal{Y}$ and the corresponding function $\rho_y(x) = (x_1 y_1 - x_2 y_2 - x_3 y_3 - x_4 y_4)^\sigma \in L_1$, we consider the linear operator $Q : L_1^* \rightarrow L_2$, defined as $u^* \mapsto F_i(\rho_y, u^*)$, which is well-defined due to the homogeneity of the functions u and v^* in the definition of the functionals F_i . It can be shown that Q intertwines the representations T_1^* and T_2 , meaning that

$$Q T_1^*(g) = T_2(g) Q \tag{3.1}$$

for all $g \in G$. However, in this context, we will only use this equality for $g = \text{id}$. Additionally, note that $dx = \sin \alpha d\alpha d\beta$ on γ_1 , $dx = \alpha d\alpha d\beta$ on γ_2 , and $dx = d\alpha d\beta$ on γ_3 .

The following theorem demonstrates that formula (??) captures the relationship between the Q -image of the basis function $f_{(0,0)}^{*(1)}$ and Q -images of functions $f_{(r,0)}^{*(2)}$.

Theorem 1. For $-\frac{7}{4} < \Re(\sigma) < -\frac{1}{4}$, the following holds:

$$\int_0^{+\infty} r [K_{\sigma+1}(r)]^2 dr = \frac{1}{2} \Gamma(2 + \sigma) \Gamma(-\sigma). \tag{3.2}$$

Proof. We express a function from B_1^* as a linear combination of the functions that constitute the basis B_2^* :

$$f_{(p,q)}^{*(1)} = \sum_{\hat{q}=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} c(p, q, r, \hat{q}) f_{(r,\hat{q})}^{*(2)} dr.$$

Since

$$\begin{aligned}
F_2(f_{(\tilde{r}, \tilde{q})}^{(2)}, f_{(p, q)}^{*(1)}) &= \sum_{\hat{q}=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} c(p, q, r, \hat{q}) F_2(f_{(\tilde{r}, \tilde{q})}^{(2)}, f_{(r, \hat{q})}^{*(2)}) dr \\
&= 2\pi \int_0^{+\infty} c(p, q, r, -\tilde{q}) \int_0^{+\infty} \alpha J_{|\tilde{q}|}(r\alpha) J_{|\tilde{q}|}(\tilde{r}\alpha) d\alpha dr \\
&= 2\pi \int_0^{+\infty} r^{-1} c(p, q, r, -\tilde{q}) \delta(r - \tilde{r}) dr = 2\pi \tilde{r}^{-1} c(p, q, \tilde{r}, -\tilde{q}),
\end{aligned}$$

where $\delta(r - \tilde{r})$ is the Dirac delta function, we have

$$c(p, q, r, \hat{q}) = (2\pi)^{-1} r F_2(f_{(r, -\hat{q})}^{(2)}, f_{(p, q)}^{*(1)}). \quad (3.3)$$

In particular,

$$c(0, 0, r, \hat{q}) = 2^{\sigma+2} \delta_{\hat{q}, 0} r \int_0^{+\infty} \alpha (1 + \alpha^2)^{-\sigma-2} J_0(r\alpha) d\alpha.$$

According to formula (see [5, Entry 2.12.4.28]),

$$\int_0^{+\infty} t^{\nu+1} (z^2 + t^2)^{-\kappa} J_\nu(ct) dt = 2^{1-\kappa} c^{\kappa-1} z^{1+\nu-\kappa} [\Gamma(\kappa)]^{-1} K_{1+\nu-\kappa}(cz), \quad (3.4)$$

where $c, \Re(z) > 0$ and $-1 < \Re(\nu) < 2\Re(\kappa) - \frac{1}{2}$, we derive

$$c(0, 0, r, \hat{q}) = 2 \delta_{\hat{q}, 0} r^{\sigma+2} [\Gamma(\sigma+2)]^{-1} K_{\sigma+1}(r). \quad (3.5)$$

Using [5, Entry 2.21.2.15], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
Q f_{(p, q)}^{*(1)}(\tilde{y}) &= F_1(\rho_{\tilde{y}}, f_{(p, q)}^{*(1)}) \\
&= \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{iq\beta} d\beta \int_0^{\pi} \sin^{q+1} \alpha C_{p-|q|}^{(|q|+1/2)}(\cos \alpha) d\alpha \\
&= 2\pi \delta_{0, q} \int_{-1}^1 C_p^{1/2}(t) dt \\
&= 4(-1)^p \delta_{0, q} \pi {}_2F_1(-p, p+1; 2; 1),
\end{aligned} \quad (3.6)$$

where ${}_2F_1$ denotes the Gauss' hypergeometric function. In particular,

$$Q f_{(0, 0)}^{*(1)}(\tilde{y}) = 4\pi. \quad (3.7)$$

Using (3.4), we derive

$$\begin{aligned}
Q f_{(p,q)}^{*(2)}(\tilde{y}) &= F_2(\rho\tilde{y}, f_{(p,q)}^{*(2)}) \\
&= 2^{-\sigma} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{iq\beta} d\beta \int_0^{+\infty} \alpha (1 + \alpha^2)^\sigma J_{|q|}(p\alpha) d\alpha \\
&= 4\pi \delta_{0,q} p^{-\sigma-1} [\Gamma(-\sigma)]^{-1} K_{\sigma+1}(p).
\end{aligned} \tag{3.8}$$

Given the linearity of Q , we have

$$Q f_{(p,q)}^{*(1)}(y) = \sum_{\hat{q}=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_0^{+\infty} c(p, q, r, \hat{q}) Q f_{(r,\hat{q})}^{*(2)}(y) dr. \tag{3.9}$$

Using (3.5), we derive from (3.9) that

$$Q f_{(0,0)}^{*(1)}(\tilde{y}) = \int_0^{+\infty} c(0, 0, r, 0) Q f_{(r,0)}^{*(2)}(\tilde{y}) dr. \tag{3.10}$$

By combining (3.5), (3.7), (3.8), and (3.10), we complete the proof. \square

Remark 1. By calculating the kernel $c(p, q, r, \hat{q})$ for arbitrary admissible values of p and q , we obtain $c(p, q, r, \hat{q}) = 0$ for $q \neq -\hat{q}$. When $q = -\hat{q}$, we can represent $C_{p-|q|}^{|q|+1/2}(p\alpha)$ as a polynomial and apply the additive property of integrals along with the formula [5, Entry 2.12.27]. The resulting integral relation between special functions, which we omit for brevity due to its complexity, can be viewed as a generalization of Theorem 1.

4. A MELLIN TRANSFORM OF ${}_3F_2$ -FUNCTION AND RELATED BARNES INTEGRAL

In this section, we establish the relationship between the Q -image of the basis function $f_{(p,q)}^{*(1)}$ and the Q -images of functions in the basis B_3^* . This relationship leads to a new formula for the inverse Mellin transform, which, when $p = q = \hat{q} = 0$, reduces to the previously known result.

Theorem 2. For $-2 < \Re(\sigma) < 0$, the following holds:

$$\begin{aligned}
&\int_{-i\infty}^{+i\infty} {}_3F_2\left(\frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 - t, 1 + p, -p; \sigma + 2, 1; 1\right) \\
&\quad \times \Gamma\left[\frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 + t, -\frac{\sigma}{2} + t, \frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 - t, -\frac{\sigma}{2} - t\right] dt \\
&= 2\pi i \Gamma(-\sigma) \Gamma(\sigma + 2) {}_2F_1(-p, p + 1; 2; 1).
\end{aligned} \tag{4.1}$$

Proof. Let us consider the linear operator:

$$f_{(p,q)}^{*(1)} = \sum_{\hat{q}=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \zeta(p, q, r, \hat{q}) f_{(r,\hat{q})}^{*(3)} dr. \tag{4.2}$$

Since $\zeta(p, q, r, \hat{q}) = (4\pi^2)^{-1} \mathbf{F}_3(f_{(-r, -\hat{q})}^{(3)}, f_{(p, q)}^{*(1)})$, according to [5, Entry 2.21.2.8], we have

$$\begin{aligned}
\zeta(p, q, r, \hat{q}) &= (4\pi^2)^{-1} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} e^{\mathbf{i}(q-\hat{q})\beta} d\beta \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \cosh^{-\sigma-2-|q|} \alpha e^{\mathbf{i}r\alpha} C_{p-|q|}^{(|q|+1/2)}(\tanh \alpha) d\alpha \\
&= (2\pi)^{-1} \delta_{q, \hat{q}} \int_{-1}^1 (1+t)^{\frac{\sigma+|q|-\mathbf{i}r}{2}} (1-t)^{\frac{\sigma+|q|+\mathbf{i}r}{2}} C_{p-|q|}^{(|q|+1/2)}(t) dt \\
&= \frac{2^{\sigma+|q|} (-1)^{p-|q|} \delta_{q, \hat{q}} (1+2|q|)_{p-|q|}}{\pi (p-|q|)!} \mathbf{B} \left(\frac{\sigma+|q|+\mathbf{i}r}{2} + 1, \frac{\sigma+|q|-\mathbf{i}r}{2} + 1 \right) \\
&\quad \times {}_3F_2 \left(|q|-p, 1+p+|q|, \frac{\sigma+|q|-\mathbf{i}r}{2} + 1; \sigma+|q|+2, 1+|q|; 1 \right), \tag{4.3}
\end{aligned}$$

where $\mathbf{B}(\mu, \nu)$ is the beta function.

Using [4, Entry 2.5.46.6], we find that

$$\begin{aligned}
Q f_{(r, \hat{q})}^{*(3)}(\tilde{y}) &= \mathbf{F}_3(\rho_{\tilde{y}}, f_{(r, \hat{q})}^{*(3)}) \\
&= 4\pi \delta_{\hat{q}, 0} \int_0^{+\infty} \cosh^\sigma \alpha \cos |r|\alpha d\alpha = \frac{\pi \delta_{\hat{q}, 0}}{2^\sigma \Gamma(-\sigma)} \Gamma \left[\frac{\mathbf{i}r - \sigma}{2}, -\frac{\mathbf{i}r + \sigma}{2} \right]. \tag{4.4}
\end{aligned}$$

From (4.2), in view of (4.4), we obtain

$$Q f_{(p, 0)}^{*(1)} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \zeta(p, 0, r, 0) Q f_{(r, 0)}^{*(3)} dr. \tag{4.5}$$

By using formulas (3.6), (4.3), (4.4), and (4.5), and applying the substitution $t = \frac{\mathbf{i}r}{2}$, we complete the proof. \square

Let us note that Theorem 2 can be verified by expanding the generalized hypergeometric function ${}_3F_2(\dots; 1)$ in integral (4.1) into a series, calculating the resulting Barnes integrals (integrating term by term), and calculating the sum of the resulting series. We emphasize that in our article this integral appeared as an expression of the relationship between the Q -images of two basis functions of the representation space.

It is noted that by setting $p = 0$ in Theorem 2 (and in (4.5), respectively), and considering (3.7), we obtain the known formula

$$\begin{aligned}
\int_{-\mathbf{i}\infty}^{+\mathbf{i}\infty} \Gamma \left[\frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 + t, -\frac{\sigma}{2} + t, -\frac{\sigma}{2} - t, \frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 - t \right] dt &= 2\pi \mathbf{i} \Gamma(-\sigma) \Gamma(\sigma + 2) \\
&(-2 < \Re(\sigma) < 0).
\end{aligned}$$

5. A REPRESENTATION OF THE MACDONALD FUNCTION AS THE INVERSE MELLIN TRANSFORM

From formulas (3.8) and (4.4), we observe that when $q \neq 0$, the basis functions $f_{(p,q)}^{*(2)}$ and $f_{(p,q)}^{*(3)}$ become zero. In Theorem 3, we show that formula (??) establishes the relationship between the Q -images of the basis functions $f_{(p,0)}^{*(2)}$ and $f_{(r,0)}^{*(3)}$.

Theorem 3. *For $-2 < \Re(\sigma) < 0$, the following holds:*

$$\int_{-i\infty}^{+i\infty} \left(\frac{p^2}{4}\right)^{-t} \Gamma\left[\frac{\sigma}{2} + 1 + t, -\frac{\sigma}{2} + t\right] dt = 4\pi i p K_{\sigma+1}(p).$$

Proof. Considering the linear operator $L_1^* \rightarrow L_1^*$ defined by formula

$$f_{(p,q)}^{*(2)} = \sum_{\hat{q}=-\infty}^{\infty} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \kappa(p, q, r, \hat{q}) f_{(r,\hat{q})}^{*(3)} dr, \quad (5.1)$$

we have the following formula for its kernel: $\kappa(p, q, r, \hat{q}) = (2\pi)^{-2} \mathbf{F}_3(f_{(-r,-\hat{q})}^{(3)}, f_{(p,q)}^{*(2)})$. Namely,

$$\kappa(p, q, r, \hat{q}) = \frac{\delta_{q,\hat{q}}}{2\pi} \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} e^{-(2+\sigma+ir)\alpha} J_{|q|}(p e^{-\alpha}) d\alpha = \frac{\delta_{q,\hat{q}}}{2\pi} \int_0^{+\infty} t^{1+\sigma+ir} J_{|q|}(pt) dt. \quad (5.2)$$

In particular, using formula [5, Entry 2.12.2.2], we obtain

$$\kappa(p, 0, r, 0) = \frac{2^{\sigma+ir}}{\pi p^{2+\sigma+ir}} \frac{\Gamma\left(1 + \frac{\sigma}{2} + \frac{ir}{2}\right)}{\Gamma\left(-\frac{\sigma}{2} - \frac{ir}{2}\right)}. \quad (5.3)$$

From (5.1), in view of (5.2), we have

$$Q f_{(p,0)}^{*(2)} = \int_{-\infty}^{+\infty} \kappa(p, 0, r, 0) f_{(r,0)}^{*(3)} dr. \quad (5.4)$$

Using formulas (3.8), (4.4), (5.3) and (5.4), we complete the proof. \square

6. CONCLUSION

In this paper, we employed only three bases of the representation space L_1^* , the simplest point of the hyperboloid \mathscr{Y} (the vertex \tilde{y}) and the simplest element of G (the identity element) for (3.1). By selecting alternative subgroups in G , different points on \mathscr{Y} and other group elements, one can derive novel generalizations of well-known formulas for integral transforms.

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